

Title: Rewriting the human story: How artificial intelligence & courageous leadership are disrupting industries, business models and rewriting the future.

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INTRODUCTION:

How startups can work with Courageous Leadership within enterprises to help push AI technologies forward within industries that have traditionally been slow to adopt new technologies

AIM:

To provide valuable insight into the ecosystem of AI innovation and identify the current organizational hurdles that are causing slow adoption of AI across enterprise companies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

BD2i has partnered with Deloitte and 8 Billion Acts of Innovation to create an AI Roadshow that will travel across Canada and the US in 2018. My presentation will consist of an overview all of the information I am able to gather regarding adoption of AI within enterprise and how AI can rewrite the human story.

RESULTS:

4 events (Toronto, New York, Mexico City and San Francisco) will culminate in a deep understanding of where AI adoption currently is, and what organizational hurdles need to be overcome to help accelerate the adoption of AI within large companies; and how they can work with startups and their own courageous leadership to accelerate that innovation.

CONCLUSIONS:

The presentation will conclude by providing answers to the following questions:

- What are the fears in enterprise organizations that prevent AI projects?
- What needs to be true in large companies to start an AI project?
- Who within the organization will need to be engaged in AI implementations and why?
- What new skills do management require to have an AI agenda?
- What's the biggest roadblock to getting an AI project in place in the next quarter, besides funding?

KEYWORDS:

Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning, Enterprise, Courageous Leadership, Innovation, Change the Future, Startups, Change Management, Early Adoption

BIOGRAPHY:

As Senior Vice President of Client Engagement, I'm responsible for deciphering business opportunities and clients' needs into artificial intelligence solutions that shape our clients' capabilities, increase revenue while reducing costs, and create platform and operational efficiencies.

My passion is working with technology-focused clients on leveraging massive movements in digital business to optimize current and future business models. I have always considered myself a "nerd" when it comes to technology and I love collaborating with our clients to help them realize how artificial intelligence can, and will, transform their business.

Education:

- Bachelor of Commerce, University of Alberta
- Bachelor of Behavioural Economics, University of Alberta